

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS OF MODE I AND MIXED-MODE DELAMINATION GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

Aspects of delamination resistance in carbon fiber/epoxy composites, including the influence of loading mode, ply interface angle and fiber bridging mechanisms, are explored using empirical methods. A resistive film crack length gauge has been developed for double cantilever beam and mixed-mode bending specimens. Load, displacements and continuous crack length measurements together with the Irwin-Kies formulation for the energy release rate are used to determine delamination resistance. For mixed-mode loading a kinematic analysis together with equilibrium conditions make it possible to derive separated mode I and mode II energy release rate data.

INTRODUCTION

Delamination beam specimens are perhaps the most familiar coupon specimen used to experimentally investigate delamination resistance. However, the models used to evaluate these experiments have been the subject of constant discussion in the literature, see e.g. Olsson [1,2]. The following work presents empirical approaches which require only the well known Irwin-Kies relation to evaluate delamination toughness. In addition to load P , displacement d , and time t , delamination length a is recorded automatically using a resistive film crack gauge suitable for narrow delamination beam profiles. Although visual/optical records of crack length are usually sufficient in quasi-static experiments, Thesken [3] introduced a delamination gauge for carbon fiber/epoxy to measure growth rate and to deal with growth instabilities. Growth instabilities become even more prevalent under mixed-mode loading making it difficult to optically measure crack length. The objective is to acquire deeper insight into the mechanisms of delamination toughness through better crack length resolution and the possibility to measure crack speed. This work is part of a larger program, overviewed by Thesken *et al.* [4], to study the transferability of a Griffith delamination growth criteria from coupon specimens to composite structures.

Double cantilever beam (DCB) and mixed-mode bending (MMB) specimens are used in these experiments. The mixed-mode bending configuration is a variation by Ljung [5] of the rig developed by Reeder and Crews [6,7]. For mixed-mode loading, the complete boundary conditions are measured; these are used in a kinematic analysis together with equilibrium conditions and the Irwin-Kies formulation to derive separated mode I and mode II energy release rate data.

Conventional delamination testing has generated much data for homogenous unidirectional lay-ups but realistic applications requires data for heterogeneous interfaces. Here it is proposed that a sandwich of one or a few off-axis plies between bulk layers of 0° material will trap a delamination and its attending damage mechanisms to create an isolated interface system. The interfaces treated thus far include: 0° , $0^\circ/5^\circ$ and $0^\circ/90^\circ$. These interfaces treated are at far ends of a spectrum of behavior. The $0^\circ/5^\circ$ are intended to prevent fiber bridging as in the small angle interface experiments by Johnson and Magalgiri [8]. The $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface is similar to the cross-ply interface studied by Wilkens *et al.* [9] where intralaminar growth in the 90° ply was observed.

CONTINUOUS CRACK GROWTH MONITORING

The graphite crack gauge used here consists of a thin graphite film in the shape of a narrow rectangular band ahead of the prospective crack path. The gauge has been used extensively for polymeric materials by Stalder *et al.* [10] who provide a thorough description of its function. As shown in Fig. 1a, voltage is applied through silver electrodes spaced a length b apart, along each side of the band. The electrodes run parallel to the crack path and extend the length L_g of the gauge.

Figure 1. a) Graphite crack gauge geometry. b) Experimentally observed trends in crack gauge resistance compared to Eqn (1), [10] also [3,11].

A simple linear relation exists between the changing gauge resistance R and crack length a as the crack separates the film:

$$\frac{R_0}{R} = 1 - \frac{a}{L_g} \quad (1)$$

where R_0 is the resistance of the initial uncracked film and a is the cracked length of the gauge. The accuracy of Eqn (1) was first checked empirically in [10] and recently by Thesken [3] and Brandt and Frii [11]. Figure 1b describes the reported trends with respect to the line representing Eqn (1). Depending on the aspect ratio b/L_g of the gauge, nonlinear behavior was observed for the beginning and end of the gauge. Therefore care must be taken in designing and positioning the gauge so that growth in the nonlinear region is avoided. Also it is recommended that an empirically determined offset factor $\delta = 0.2(b/L_g)$ is added to the right hand side of Eqn (1), see Fig 1b.

Two technical problems arise when applying the graphite crack gauge to delamination growth measurements in carbon fiber composites. The first is the requirement to insulate the conductive film from the underlying carbon fibers. The second problem is the limited space available on the narrow profile of common delamination specimens. The latter problem places design constraints on the gauge dimensions, electrode resistance, initial film resistance and also introduces manufacturing difficulties. The peculiarities of gauge design, insulation and application for delamination measurements in carbon fiber composites have been discussed by Thesken [3]. Brandt and Frii [11] describe ways to streamline the manufacturing technique so that a batch of 12 specimens can be made in roughly 3-4 days.

Gauge dimensions in the following studies were kept so that $b/L_g \leq 0.1$. For such gauges, results in [10] indicates that $\pm 1\%$ accuracy is achievable in the linear range $0.4 b/L_g < a/L_g < 0.95$. The graphite crack gauges had an initial resistance of 100 to 300 ohm. Low relative electrode resistance is important to gauge accuracy, especially for narrow profiles [3]. The silver electrode resistance was kept to less than 1% of the initial gauge resistance. Recently this was improved to 0.1% by using copper foil electrodes instead of silver paint. The copper foil is bonded to the insulated specimen and made into two separate and highly parallel electrodes by cutting it with the precision controlled scalpel described in [11].

The measurement circuit consisted of a shunt resistor placed in series with the gauge and a battery. The measured voltage across the shunt resistor can be considered proportional to $1/R$ and to crack length; the exact relations are given in [3]. The graphite crack gauge has been evaluated in comparison to delamination measurements made visually, with microscopy and from radiographs of DCB tests [3,11]. Thesken and Henriksson [12] have also shown good agreement between delamination gauge measurements and acoustic emission location in DCB tests. Further testing of the gauge's linearity and accuracy was made by applying the gauge to a PMMA plate and using a precision controlled scalpel to simulate crack growth [11]. These results [3,11,12] indicates that the gauge has the resolution necessary for crack growth measurements.

LAY-UP AND SPECIMEN PREPARATION

The 0°, 0°/5° and 0°/90° interfaces for the delamination beam specimens were created from the following respective lay-ups: 0°₂₄, (0°₁₂/±5°/0°₈/±5°) and (0°₁₂/90°/0°₁₂). A 13 μm thick Al-foil coated with Teflon™ paint was inserted after the 12th unidirectional layer in all cases as an artificial flaw. The 24 plies specimen had a nominal width and thickness of 20.0 mm and 3.0 mm respectively and were cut to a length of ≥145 mm with an initial crack length of 25 mm. After sectioning, specimens were insulated according to procedures outlined in [3,11]. Loading hinges were then applied before the graphite crack gauge was stencilled into place.

DOUBLE CANTILEVER BEAM TESTS

The DCB testing follows standard procedures [13]; further details may be found in [11]. Load, displacements and the crack gauge voltage are acquire by a Macintosh PC equipped with WorkBench™ software. Travelling microscope measurements and a macro-ccd camera/video recorder were also used to follow growth. For most cases the displacement was observed to return to zero when the specimen was unloaded. This means that the load, displacement and continuous crack length data can be used to generate continuous delamination resistance curves in a simple procedure [3]. First specimen compliance *C* is evaluated as $C = d/P$ from the load and displacement data and plotted against *a*. The derivative dC/da is then determined from a curve fit. The energy release rate *G* can then be evaluated as a function of crack length using the Irwin-Kies formula.

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2w} \frac{dC}{da} \tag{2}$$

where *w* is specimen width. Experimental data for a 0° interface is used to illustrate this point in Fig. 2. A continuous crack length *a* vs *d* curve is shown in Fig. 2a and the corresponding *C* vs *a* curve shown in Fig. 2b. A numerically computed curve fit to the data is also shown in Fig. 2b. Several different types of curve fits have been examined in the study including: polynomial, logarithmic, exponential and power law. The choice of curve fit was made to give the best fit in the initiation and early growth region of the data. Figure 2c shows an example of the resulting delamination toughness curve. Note the existence of upper and lower critical point which is associated with blunt starter cracks and the resin zone that occurs in front of thick inserts. This was a characteristic of the 0° and 0°/5° interfaces. The results for all three interface cases are summarized in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. DCB results and data reduction. a) Crack length versus displacement data. b) Compliance versus crack length plot with curve fit to determine dC/da . c) Continuous delamination toughness curve showing upper and lower critical points.

Figure 3. Summary of DCB delamination toughness curves. a) 0° interface b) 0°/5° interface c) 0°/90° interface.

Images from the macro-ccd camera were recorded on video tape and later examined in an image analysis program [11]. The results show very clear differences in the respective fiber bridging processes. Three examples for each interface are shown in Fig. 4. As expected, fiber intermingling along the 0° interface produces large scale bridging zone in Fig. 4a. However, in Fig. 4b the population of bridging fibers is extremely reduced and the length of the zone shortened for the $0^\circ/5^\circ$ interface. The $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface in Fig. 4c is clearly intralaminar fracture as the crack front winds its way through the 90° fibers in the manner of a cross-slipping screw dislocation. This action releases bundles of bridging fibers which lie parallel to the crack front and the bridging zone is nearly as long as the newly grown crack. Radiographs of the three interfaces also appear in Fig. 4a,b&c. The crack front curvature of the 0° and $0^\circ/5^\circ$ interfaces show the familiar concave shape reported in earlier studies [14], however, the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface shows a convex curve front.

Figure 4. a) Macro-fractography of bridging and a radiograph of a 0° interface crack front.
 b) Macro-fractography of bridging and a radiograph of a $0^\circ/5^\circ$ interface crack front.
 c) Macro-fractography of bridging and a radiograph of a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface crack front.

MIXED-MODE BENDING TESTS

The mixed-mode testing was made with a variation of the Reeder and Crews [6,7] mixed-mode bending rig developed by Ljung [5] shown in Fig. 5a. Using unidirectional beams of HTA/6376C Ljung [5] reports delamination toughness for several mixed-mode ratios versus percentage G_{II} , see Fig. 5b. This work has been extended here in two ways: 1) to fully determine the kinematic motion of the loading lever and its components during a mixed-mode test. 2) to use empirical measurements to determine the mixed-mode ratio during testing.

The first objective required measuring two vertical displacements and one horizontal displacement during each experiment. As shown in Fig. 5a, horizontal and vertical displacements, d_h, d_v , are measured at the applied loading point and a vertical displacement, d_c , is measured at the loading fulcrum. Geometry then determines the displacements associated with the mode I opening load, d_I , and mode II flexural load, d_{II} . Care must be taken in determining the correct displacement value for d_{II} ; it is not by itself the measured vertical displacement, d_c , of the fulcrum. Figure 6 describes a first approximation of the correct kinematic relationship to determine d_{II} . The figure shows a DCB specimen which has been loaded in a fashion which maintains a zero load contact with the rear support of the MMB rig.

Figure 5 a) FFA version of the MMB rig [5]. b) Delamination toughness versus mode mixture [5].

Figure 6. Kinematics for the correct determination of d_{II} , the distance through which P_{II} acts.

Figure 7. Superposition of mode I and mode II components in the MMB rig [6,7].

This indicates that the mode II flexural load must act through a displacement, Δ , in addition to d_c . The value of Δ is determined by similar triangles. This approach is based purely on kinematics; Giannakopoulos [15] has pointed out that a complete analysis must include deformations which might be caused by the fulcrum as it acts to bring the beam into a zero load contact with the rear support. Unfortunately this contribution would require the evaluation of a crack length dependent model for each increment of growth and negate the purely empirical evaluation of G_I and G_{II} .

The second objective relies on the application of the Irwin-Kies formulation (2) described earlier to both components of the mixed-mode superposition. Reeder and Crews [6,7] have worked out the equilibrium conditions for the superposed load systems shown in Fig. 7. The respective mode I, P_I and mode II, P_{II} load components are proportional to the applied load P by the following equations

$$P_I = \frac{(3c-L)}{4L} P \quad (3a)$$

$$P_{II} = \frac{(c+L)}{L} P \quad (3b)$$

where c is defined in Fig. 5a.

Using the compliance equation $C = d/P$, the geometric relations for d_I and d_{II} , and crack growth measurements it is possible to construct compliance versus crack length curves for each load displacement pair. Curve fits are then used to determine dC/da vs a ; this function is then used to complete the Irwin-Kies evaluation, Eqn (2), of G , G_I and G_{II} .

The data acquisition system is the same as for the DCB experiments. Two additional instrumented dial gauges were used to measure the horizontal displacement and the vertical fulcrum displacement. The vertical displacement of the applied load point was measured as in the DCB experiments. The experiments were set to achieve a balanced 1/1 mode mixture; $c = 41$ mm was chosen based on the finite element analysis of Reeder and Crews [6].

A complete example of the empirical analysis is provided for one test case. Figure 8a presents the load displacement curves for the three load displacement pairs. Again P_I and P_{II} are determined by equilibrium considerations and d_I and d_{II} are determined from the kinematics of the lever/ fulcrum system. As a check, load displacement data for pure mode I DCB and pure mode II ENF tests are superimposed to show that the initial and final stiffnesses are reasonable (see Fig. 8b&c).

Occasionally growth instabilities occurred which the 5 Hz sampling frequency could not resolve but the gauge quickly relocates the crack tip. This is evident in the a vs d plot in Fig. 9a. Corresponding compliance curves are shown in Fig. 9b. Continuous G , G_I and G_{II} delamination toughness curves for these results are shown in Fig. 9c. The ratio of G_I/G_{II} is plotted in Fig. 10a, it is within 4% of the finite element results in [6]. Since $G = G_I + G_{II}$, a satisfactory check of the calculations is made in Fig. 10b. Examples of delamination toughness results for $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface are given in Fig. 10c.

Figure 8. a) Load versus displacement plots for each load/displacement pair in a MMB test, 0° interface. b) Comparison of the mode I plot to a DCB test result from ref [11]. c) Comparison of the mode II plot to an ENF test result from ref [5].

Figure 9. a) Crack length versus applied displacement for a 0° interface. b) Compliance versus crack length curves for each load/ displacement pair in Fig. 8a. c) Delamination toughness in terms of total G and the separated components G_I and G_{II} .

Figure 10. a) Ratio of mode I to mode II energy release rate versus crack length. b) Comparison of the sum $G_I + G_{II}$ to the empirically determined total G . c) Examples of delamination toughness for a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface.

Figure 11. Macro-fractographs of bridging in MMB tests. a) 0° interface. b) Crack kinks at initiation (see arrow) and grows along the other $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface without further bridging.

Fiber bridging was heavily reduced for all interfaces in the MMB tests; Fig. 11 presents results for the 0° and $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces which can be compared to Fig. 4. The reduction is particularly obvious for the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface specimens where the only fiber bridge is in the form of kink occurring at initiation, see Fig. 11b.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Continuous delamination resistance curves were determined by the Irwin-Kies relation with the aid of measurements from a graphite crack gauge. Extension of the approach to fully instrumented mixed-mode bending tests was demonstrated. Here the utility of the gauge is clear, since it would be impossible to manually measure crack length in the presence of the observed growth instabilities. Mode separation of the global mode mixture was achieved based upon empirical determination of the mode I and mode II load/displacement pairs and the Irwin-Kies relation. It should be mentioned the empirically determined mode ratios are within about 4% with those computed by Reeder and Crews [6] for the same rig parameters.

Fiber bridging zones in both DCB and MMB tests were monitored by a macro-ccd camera. The amount of bridging for each interface in the DCB test was distinctly different. Although the amount of bridging fibers for the $0^\circ/5^\circ$ interface was less than in the 0° interface, there was no clear difference in the delamination growth resistance data for these two interfaces. The $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface developed intralaminar fracture with substantial bridging parallel to the crack front. Accordingly, the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface has the highest mode I delamination growth resistance. Although not reported here, growth rates decreased with increasing delamination toughness in the DCB tests. This is consistent with the increasing size of the bridging zone seen in the video recordings of the tests.

The mode II loading component in the MMB test completely changes these observations. Fiber bridging was substantially reduced for all interfaces, including for the $0^\circ/5^\circ$ interface which was not shown. The most significant change was for the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface. There the delamination kinked across the 90° ply to the upper interface and remained trapped during the remainder of growth. The only fiber bridging was a bundle of fibers at the kink and delamination growth resistance decreased with crack growth. For the 0° interface, mixed-mode delamination growth resistance decreased through the initial growth and then increased at the end. Growth rates have yet to be evaluated but they were considerably greater than in the DCB tests. A sampling frequency of 5 Hz was insufficient to resolve the detail of some growth instabilities but the crack gauge could quickly relocate the crack tip after these jumps.

A few difficulties are noted in these experiments and are the subject of further work. The occurrence of wide variations of mode I initiation toughness values and the presence of upper/lower critical behavior seen in Figs. 3a and b is linked to two problems. Physically these variations are caused by the blunt resin zone at the tip of the artificial flaw. This effect combined with inaccuracies in curve fitting procedures at end points of the compliance-crack length curve, leads to uncertainty in the initiation toughness. Presently an artificial flaw consisting of a $1.5\ \mu\text{m}$ thick metal foil coated with Teflon™ is being studied as means to provide a sharper flaw. Better numerical algorithms for making curve fits and taking derivatives of experimental data are also under investigation.

A closer look at some of the load versus displacement curves revealed nonlinearities which are presently attributed to poor tolerances and flexibility of specimen hinges. Also during MMB testing the adhesive bonding the specimen hinges would occasionally fail. Therefore a new loading hinge system has been designed with tighter dimensional tolerances and constructed of steel. The

new hinges do not require adhesive bonding to the specimen. They are securely fastened using a set screw arrangement which also makes mounting/unmounting simple.

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